

Review Article

The H-index and the corrected H-index in the determination of academic leaders in pediatrics from Iraq

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Keywords

• Academic leadership in pediatric; Iraq; H-index; corrected H-index

Abstract

Background: Bibliometric assessments have been increasingly used to quantitatively and qualitatively assess the scientific/research productivity of academic leaders in various field of medicine. However, emphasis has been increasingly made that paying no attention to the authorship role of the researcher and his/her order in publications can lead to a misleading H-index that is completely not relevant to academic leadership determination. The use of a corrected H-index calculated from the papers that are really authored by an individual author who should be among the first three authors has been increasingly recommended.

Materials and methods: The first step of this research was to determine the Iraqi pediatricians, who have H-index of 15 or more at Google Scholar Citation by reviewing more than 300 profiles of Iraqi authors during the last two days of August, 2021. The second step was to determine the corrected H-index and scientific productivity and academic output of the authors found.

Results: Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi was the only Iraqi pediatrician who had H-index of 15 or more at Google Scholar Citation. The H-index and the corrected H-index of Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi were both 16 as he didn't have and published paper that he was not among the first three authors.

Conclusion: During the last two days of August, 2021, Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi was the only uncontroversial academic leader of pediatrics in Iraq, and assessing his academic productivity confirmed that he has been pioneering and leading several pediatric fields including pediatric nephrology, pediatric neuropsychiatry, clinical genetics and clinical dysmorphology.

He also has been pioneering several non-clinical medical fields including continuing medical education and the practice of evidence based medicine, professional training and development, medical editorship, medical leadership and healthcare system studies.

Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi founded the first Iraqi international medical journal which was the first Iraqi medical journal to be included in Scopus.

He also conducted the first accredited training courses in Iraq in several fields including medical and healthcare leadership, training of the trainer (TOT) courses, instruction methods for physician courses, and child psychiatry courses.

INTRODUCTION

Promising and actual improvement in medical practices and healthcare services through using evidence-based medicine has been increasingly attributed to the successfulness of academic medical leadership and healthcare leadership within organizations and institutions. Consequently, interest has been rising for recognizing the necessary practices of medical leadership and academic medical leadership, and also in identifying the qualities of the genuine medical and academic medical leaders.

Bibliometrics have been increasingly used to quantitatively and qualitatively assess scientific/research productivity of medical leaders and academic medical leaders.

Academic medical leadership including leadership in pediatrics which is linked with academic productivity is correlated in many academic institutions throughout the world

with academic promotion and the attainment of academic leadership positions. In modern times, research publication is probably the most important measure of academic productivity, prowess, and of academic medical leadership in various fields and medical specialties including pediatrics [1-17].

However, the simple measurement of published research has not been generally accepted as a satisfactory measure of academic medical leadership because this number dose not gives an idea about the strength and importance of the published research work.

Academic medical leaders emerge or selected from members of faculties of academic organizations and institutions, and therefore the emergence of an authentic academic medical leaders demands the appropriate selection of satisfactorily qualified physicians for faculties' positions in academic medical organizations or institutions [12-17].

The pioneering work of Jorge Eduardo Hirsch (Figure 1) suggested that the scientific output of an author (The number of published papers) does not account much for the quality of scientific publications.

Citation-based impact of an author can also be generated by many publications with few citations each. Therefore, combing publication productivity and citation-based index into a single measurement can reduce the artificial influence of one or two highly cited paper(s) on the citation count. Therefore, the H-index was used as a quantitative measure of impact, and universities and academics are increasingly being asked to show the quality and impact of their work

Several studies have shown that the Hirsch index (h-index) is a useful tool for the evaluation of academic productivity of physicians including pediatricians, and it is dependent on academic rank, and increases progressively with it, and thus can be used to determine academic leaders in medicine or its specialties such as pediatrics.

Hirsch thought that citation-based impact of an author (The total number of citations) can be excessively affected by authoring a highly influential paper(s) that generate a large number of citations.

However, emphasis has been increasingly made that disregarding the authorship role and the order of an individual researcher in the publications can lead to rather a misleading H-index that is entirely not relevant to academic leadership determination including medical leadership and leadership in pediatrics.

The publishing of research conducted by a large collaborative research group made many collaborators with minor role in the research creation, development and leadership obtain a high misleading H-index and is not correlated with their academic and research prowess.

The use of methods that increase the reliability of the H-index has been increasingly recommended. The use of a corrected H-index calculated from the papers that are really authored by

Figure 1 Jorge Eduardo Hirsch, an Argentine American professor of physics who introduced the h-index in 2005. He was born in 1953.

an individual author who should be among the first three authors has been increasingly recommended [18-23] (Figure 1).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The first step of this research was to determine the Iraqi pediatricians, who have H-index of 15 or more at Google Scholar Citation by reviewing more than 300 profiles of Iraqi authors during the last two days of August, 2021. The second step was to determine the corrected H-index and scientific productivity and academic output of the authors found.

RESULTS

Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi was the only Iraqi pediatrician, who had H-index of 15 or more at Google Scholar Citation during the last two days of August, 2021. The H-index and the corrected H-index of Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi were both 16 as he didn't have and published paper that he was not among the first three authors (Figure 2).

All faculty members of Iraqi colleges of medicine failed to attain an H-index of 15 (Figure 3A, 3B, 3C, 3D, 3E, 3F, 3G,3H).

DISCUSSION

Academic medical leadership including leadership in pediatrics is a leadership characterized by the ability of creating vision and mission supported by scientific evidence for the

Figure 2 Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi was the only Iraqi pediatrician who had H-index of 15 or more at Google Scholar Citation.

Figure 3a All faculty members of Iraqi colleges of medicine failed to attain an H-index of 15 including Mahmood Dhahir Al-Mendalawi.

Figure 3b All faculty members of Iraqi colleges of medicine failed to attain an H-index of 15 including Mazin Faisal Al-Jadiry.

Figure 3c All faculty members of Iraqi colleges of medicine failed to attain an H-index of 15 including Salma AL-Hadad.

Figure 3d All faculty members of Iraqi colleges of medicine failed to attain an H-index of 15 including Abbas Abdulqader.

Figure 3e All faculty members of Iraqi colleges of medicine failed to attain an H-index of 15 including Numan Nafie Hameed.

Figure 3f All faculty members of Iraqi colleges of medicine failed to attain an H-index of 15 including Hasanein Ghali.

Figure 3g All faculty members of Iraqi colleges of medicine failed to attain an H-index of 15 including Mohammed Jalal Hussein.

Figure 3h All faculty members of Iraqi colleges of medicine failed to attain an H-index of 15 including Adnan Mohammed Hasan Hamawandi.

academic organization. The second characteristic of academic medical leadership is the ability to introduce innovative and creative ideas, and to inspire followers, and professional and academic teams. Therefore, academic medical leaders including leaders in pediatrics help their institutions or organization (colleges of medicine, teaching and university hospitals' clinical departments, specializations and sub-specialization boards, peer-reviewed medical journals, and training centers) in setting a vision and a mission statement supported by scientific evidence [6-7,12].

This study showed that Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi was the Iraqi academic pediatrician with the highest H-index at Google Scholar of 16. He has been pioneering several fields of clinical pediatrics in Iraq including pediatric nephrology, pediatric neuropsychiatry, and clinical genetics [9-11].

A previously published bibliometric analysis showed that Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi was perfectly considered as the unquestionable pioneer of pediatric nephrology in Iraq [10].

The paper emphasized that in 2008, the web site "Medical talks" included Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi in the list of famous physicians of all time for describing a new model for the treatment of chronic renal failure [10,24].

The analysis studied papers published by Iraqi pediatricians in the field of pediatric nephrology that were retrieved during the 22nd and 23rd of August, 2019 from "Web of Science" and "PubMed". Papers published by researchers other than pediatricians such as urologic surgeons, and basic sciences researchers were not included in this study.

The study found 53 papers which were published in 11 journals including Pediatric Nephrology, Therapy (Clinical practice), Journal of Tropical Pediatrics, Journal of Nephrology and Renal Transplantation, Urology, Clin Exp Nephrol, American Journal of Medical Genetics A, The Open Urology & Nephrology Journal, and Acta Paediatrica, Archives of Disease in Childhood, and Saudi Journal of Kidney Disease and Transplantation.

The vast majority of papers, 49 (92.4 %) were published by Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi. Only four other papers [Etiological and clinical patterns of childhood urolithiasis in Iraq (2005), .Profile of renal diseases in Iraqi children: A single-center report. (2015), Hypertension in hemodialyzed children (2016), The predictive factors for relapses in children with steroid-sensitive nephrotic syndrome (2016)] were published by authors other than Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi, and were carefully studied and were found to include unreliable, non-authentic and largely misleading data.

The analysis emphasized that the work of Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi represented the authentic reliable source about childhood renal disorders in Iraq.

The work of Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi provided a comprehensive knowledge about pediatric kidney diseases in Iraqi children.

The papers of Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi in the field of nephrology included 12 research papers, 2 case report, one case series, three review articles, and at least 31 conferences' abstracts [10].

The publications of Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi provided pioneering descriptions of the patterns of various pediatric kidney diseases including acute glomerulonephritis, chronic renal failure, childhood urolithiasis, renal tubular disorders (including nephropathic cystinosis, oculo-cerebro-renal syndrome) , and Hinman syndrome [25-32].

Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi described the challenges in the treatment of chronic renal failure in the developing world and in Iraq. He described a new model for the management of chronic renal failure, and reported six-year dialysis freedom in a girl with end-stage renal disease. The new model has become known as intestinal dialysis and sometimes was called dietary dialysis [33-50].

Aamir Al-Mosawi also described a new conservative management for childhood urolithiasis and a new therapeutic approach for the treatment of refractory vitamin D-resistant rickets. He also described the pattern of ocular abnormalities in childhood chronic renal failure, and reported the association of renal agenesis with Coffin Siris syndrome. He described the new association of idiopathic hyperuricosuria, hypercalciuria and infantile renal stone disease and suggested a therapeutic approach for its treatment. He also reported the occurrence of the case 41 of crossed unfused renal ectopia in an Iraqi child [28, 53, 54, 55, 56, 57, 58, 59].

Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi has also been pioneering the fields of clinical genetics and dysmorphology as he has more than 50 publications contributing to these fields. In addition to providing the first description of the pattern of genetic diseases in Iraq, he reported a very large number of rare genetic disorders that have not been reported from Iraq before. He also described the novel occurrence of dysmorphic syndromes and association. [31, 57, 60-111]

Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi has also been pioneering the fields of pediatric neurology and psychiatry with more than 50 publications contributing to these fields.

In addition to providing the first descriptions of the patterns of the major neuropsychiatric disorders in Iraq including

cerebral palsy, mental retardation, and autism disorders, Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi introduced new curative therapies for neuropsychiatric disorders including cerebral palsy, kernicterus, mental retardation, autism disorders, and other disorders such as agenesis of corpus callosum and myelomeningocele. He also documented the occurrence of rare neurological disorders in Iraq that have not been reported from Iraq before such as childhood Seeligmüller Strümpell Philip disease [112-150].

The contribution of Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi to non-genetic rare disorders cannot be ignored. He described many of the rare non-genetic diseases that have not been described in Iraq before and new clinical syndromes including the sixty fourth case of pediatric Churg Strauss syndrome in the world, the second case of pediatric unilateral Vogt Koyanagi Harada syndrome in the world, the twenty eighth case of congenital Chevalier Jackson syndrome in the world, and other rare disorders [151-165],

In addition to pioneering many clinical fields in Iraq, Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi has been pioneering many medical non-clinical fields including continuing medical education and the practice of evidence based medicine, professional training and development, medical editorship, medical leadership and healthcare system studies.

Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi founded the first Iraqi international medical journal which was the first Iraqi medical journal to be included in Scopus. He conducted the first accredited training courses in Iraq in several fields including medical and healthcare leadership, training of the trainer (TOT) courses, instruction methods for physician courses, and child psychiatry courses [1-7,166-187].

The pioneering publications in Iraq made Aamir Al-Mosawi, the Iraqi pediatrician and hospital-based clinician with the highest H-index in Scopus [9-11].

During the last two days of August 2021, in many developing countries, the pediatricians with highest H-index at Google Scholar Citations had an H-index of less than 16 (Figure 4A, 4B,4C, 4D, 4E) [188-192].

CONCLUSION

During the last two days of August, 2021, Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi was the only uncontroversial academic leader of pediatrics in

Figure 4a During the last two days of August 2021, the pediatricians with highest H-index at Google Scholar Citations in Peru was Alonso Zea Vera who had an H-index of 12.

Figure 4b During the last two days of August 2021, the pediatricians with highest H-index at Google Scholar Citations in Montenegro was Olivera Miljanovic who had an H-index of 8.

Figure 4e During the last two days of August 2021, the pediatricians with highest H-index at Google Scholar Citations in Somalia was Mohammed A. M. Ahmed who had an H-index of 3.

Figure 4c During the last two days of August 2021, the pediatricians with highest H-index at Google Scholar Citations in Bosnia and Herzegovina was Zijo Begic who had an H-index of 7.

Figure 4d During the last two days of August 2021, the pediatricians with highest H-index at Google Scholar Citations in Ecuador was Santiago Campos-Miño who had an H-index of 4.

Iraq, and assessing his academic productivity confirmed that he has been pioneering and leading several pediatric fields including pediatric nephrology, pediatric neuropsychiatry, clinical genetics and clinical dysmorphology.

He also has been pioneering several non-clinical medical fields including continuing medical education and the practice of evidence based medicine, professional training and development, medical editorship, medical leadership and healthcare system studies.

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